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Team Teaching Experiences in Engineering Education A Project-Based Learning Approach

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ABSTRACT

As a part of the new Curriculum development, teaching and learning methods were piloted in the ICT department during the past years. The aim for this study was to find out how teaching and learning are changed with relation to traditional higher education. According to the results the team teaching will be adopted to the whole organization.

The new Curriculum is based on 30 ECTS credits semester projects due to results of piloting other options as well. Learning projects are based on an agreement with either local industry or University's R&D&I projects. Eight (8) semesters were designed by named teacher teams who will also implement the future projects. Each team was comprised of professors from various fields.

In this research team-teaching was found to give better learning results and enlarge teachers' know-how. Team-teaching and project based learning (PBL) give more opportunities to develop industrial cooperation and makes easier for students to get a professional job after graduation. As measurable values the student satisfaction factor has raised as well as the total number of credit points students have completed annually.

Conference Key Areas: Curriculum Development

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INTRODUCTION

The Development of the New Curriculum 2017 in Lapland University of Applied Sciences is based on the process which was started when the decision to merge two independent Universities of Applied Sciences, Rovaniemi and Kemi-Tornio, was done. The merging of these two Universities was realized on 1st January 2014. Both universities had same faculties and the overlapping in fields of studies caused a pressure to harmonize curricula as much as possible.

The Ministry of Education in Finland is measuring the effectiveness of teaching in Universities by key figures e.g. completion percentage, the number of students who have completed at least 55 ECTS annually and statistics of the annual feedback of students. This is due to performance-based funding. To meet these key figures has been demanding especially in the ICT education. It was obvious that the new pedagogical tools were needed. Lapland UAS started the new curriculum development process and the degree program of ICT was a forerunner to pilot new learning methods.

This paper discusses the introduction of developing new curriculum based on PBL and piloting it with different student groups and organizing learning by teacher teams. The data includes quantitative as well as qualitative information that was collected from students and teachers during and after each pilot. At first paper introduces the idea of project based curriculum and how semester projects were developed using collaborative teacher teams. Second, the planning and implementation of the reformed curriculum is explained. Third, the results of pilots collected from different student teams and teacher interviews are analyzed. Finally, conclusions for further research and development are presented.

1 CURRICULUM STRUCTURE

1.1 Semester Projects

The core of each semester is a learning and/or problem solving project which is supported by the other courses of the semester. The subject matters of the courses are integrated to the project, and build upon the know-how intended for the semester along with the project.

The Project competence of students evolves along with studies on these semester long projects. These projects are large entities that combine all the subjects of the semester into an entity that provides a concrete end result as shown in *Fig. 1*. More detailed description of the structure of the seasonal projects with some examples can be found in the reference [1]. For students learning general principles of project management and team skills necessary to accomplish a common goal are the primary goals of the first year. Second year is to acquaint students with Agile methods in a project management context. The third year focuses on advanced project management skills, quality assurance and working in a customer interface. These project studies prepare the students for acting as a project manager and taking responsibility in large information systems' development projects.

Fig 1. Fundamentals of the Semester Structure in Curriculum

2 SEMESTER PLANNING AND IMPLEMENTATION

2.1 Planning phase

The semester planning process starts by getting the customers representatives and a team of teachers around the same table. The teacher team consist of teachers who will have their courses during the semester. The number of teachers is usually 5-6. An example of annual operating plan is illustrated in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. The Annual Operating Plan example

The learning targets of the season and the courses are gathered and gone over by the teacher team. After that an assignment for completing the learning targets is constructed. The end result is the first draft of the assignment for students.

The assignment is deconstructed in a way that in each course the elements that support the project are defined and listed. Some decisions about the interconnected subject matters of the courses may have to be made. The end result is a list of courses and the subject matters that support the project.

The organization model is chosen for the learning project, for example a generic project management and implementation model or one of the agile methods, e.g. SCRUM. SCRUM method is widely used in the other Universities as well. For example, University of Århus, Denmark, is using it in teaching according to reference [2]. The teacher team makes decisions on, among other things, the times to start and end, the amount of mutual reviews, ways of guidance, etc. The timing for each of the courses that support the project is defined. The end result is a table shown in a Fig. 3 that indicates the timing of the courses of the semester. The table helps to manage and understand the outline of the project as well as to calculate the weekly load of the students. The information from the Excel table is moved to SoleOPS resource management system.

Fig. 3. An Example of the scheduling chart of one semester

2.2 Implementation phase

The teacher team have meetings on a regular basis with representatives of customers. In these meetings the progress, the status and procedures of the project groups are reviewed. The teacher team itself operates according to the methods of project management.

The progress reviews of the project groups are events that are scheduled already at the planning phase. In the review each project group pitch the team's current results. In the event the status of the project managing is evaluated as well. The teacher team gives the feedback and guides the groups in technical problems and in the project implementation process itself. At the end of the review day the teacher team continue with a meeting where subjects that have come up are discussed. Also if a more detailed help is needed the responsibilities are agreed and some team and individual assessment is done. If there have emerged any possible problem areas in the student teams, teachers can intervene early enough. Virtual learning environments, like Moodle and iLinc, are used during these learning projects for support and documentation.

During the process there are varying amount of teaching moments that support the implementation of the project in the allocated courses in forms of laboratory and workshop exercises, and lectures. The contents of these moments are decided in the planning process by the teacher team. Part of the problems in the project may be unforeseen and in these cases each teacher tries to bring their ad hoc support to the project. A workspace is provided to the students where they can act to complete the project when the opportunity rises during the working week. The teacher team aspires to be available in problem situations and tries at the very least to cheer on the students in the projects.

The season finale is a coordinated closure which is made to be as grandiose as possible. Exhibitions aimed to a large audience – at least to other students – are a great way to achieve this. The final event of semester is prepared meticulously and all exhibition goods must be made ready beforehand. The awareness of the exhibition creates a right amount of creative pressure for the whole season. According to [3] teams are able to generate lot of new ideas, but if they do not operate in the proper environment, which affords them a supportive and participative context with excellence of task performance, team creativity will not be translated to innovation implementation. The teacher team assesses the finished project in the event, where all of the results of the courses that are integrated to a one big entirety. The finale ends for the teachers in a final evaluation. The evaluation can naturally include course related subjects that are not included to the project, but the shared subjects are evaluated together.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Statistics

During the curriculum development process required quality statistics were gathered during three years. As mentioned in the Introduction the key figures e.g completion percentage, the number of students who have completed over 55 ECTS and statistics of annual feedback of students has been collected either yearly basis or at the end of each course and project to get information for further progress.

Table 1. Over 55 ECTS achieved students

Group	The amount of Students	>55 ECTS (%)
T12	15	14
T13	25	64
T14	32	47
T15	41	88

The information in the *Table 1.* shows how the percentage of achieved ECTS have varied between three student groups in the pilots. The group T12 studied with the traditional curriculum; groups T13, T14 and T15 had PBL based Curriculums. The pilot shows significant difference in the achieved ECTS. For the group T14 were made a test without a semester project and the result was immediate as seen in the *Table 1,* which was also found out in the student feedback.

The Student feedback is collected according to *Table 2.*

Table 2. Student feedback (scale 1...7).

The Feedback Subject	ICT Department (all groups)	University (total)
CONTENT AND IMPLEMENTATION OF STUDIES	5,18	4,80
STUDYING AND STUDENT SUPPORT SERVICES	5,40	5,12
GUIDANCE IN STUDYING AND LEARNING	5,17	4,69
COLLABORATION WITH WORKING LIFE	4,37	4,59
DEVELOPMENT OF COMPETENCE	5,18	5,21
SATISFACTION WITH LAPLAND UAS	5,42	5,05

Behind the average figures in the *Table 2.* there are more detailed yearly based numbers that shows also the effect of the new PBL based curriculum.

Compared to the older statistics the continuous improvement have been achieved, but there is still work to do. Even though most of the results are above the university average there is for example the “Collaboration with working life” that has arisen some questions. One answer to this question was found from the written feedback and discussions with students: Although learning projects were industry based and there were real customers, all students didn’t realize this as a collaboration with working life.

Students’ free written feedback gives also good information in further development. Student feedback experiences has been similar in [4], especially they found out

significant improvement in the student progression.

3.2 Experiences

The new project based Curriculum has shown it's effectiveness during the pilots with different student groups. Projects are real life projects either from local companies or R&D-projects with other stakeholders. The suitable courses are integrated to the project and learning is done according to the same rules as in working life in real companies and projects.

Teachers are not working alone and more effort and time have to be used for the semester project planning. This brings also the company representatives closer to the university while they are also invited to the planning phase and to visit or give the information to students' "companies" that are working with the project. Teacher experiences are shown in *Table 3*.

Table 3. Teacher feedback.

To be noticed	Was worth to
Everything to the master time table	Working together is nice and fun
Meaning of the preplanning phase is significant	Very instructive
First time very challenging, repetition makes it easier	Not bored
Evaluation is worth to complete together in the teacher team if possible	Problem solving together makes it easier
Planning phase should be started as early as possible	The joint assessment will support your own decisions
Reviews takes some time from the "ancient" one-way lectures in resource planning	The project team of students carry each other
Suitable and accessible space is required for self-oriented project workshops	Better completion percentage
Physical location of the teacher team as close to workshops as possible	Continuous learning
Teacher team located very close to each other to ensure the open communication	
The beginning is always difficult	
New culture requires change in attitude, others are slower than the others	
Project management and teamwork skills are required	

The results are satisfactory and very similar to described in reference [5]. The change is required not just as a form of new curriculars but in attitudes and management support (leadership). The final completion percentage can't be measured yet, it'll be possible earliest at year 2018.

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